

FATIGUE STRENGTH CHARACTERISATION OF WIRE+ARC ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED STEEL COMPONENTS AND THE RELATION WITH MANUFACTURING IMPERFECTIONS

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In this paper, the fatigue performance of two steels (denoted as EMK8 and 1%Ni) produced by wire+arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) is characterised by rotating bending fatigue experiments. Specimens were extracted from thin walls and thick blocks in both X- (deposition) and Z- (build) directions. The walls produced from EMK8 showed statistically relevant anisotropy in fatigue performance. No significant anisotropy was observed for the blocks of EMK8 material, nor for the 1%Ni material. The experimentally obtained S-N curves of both materials were also benchmarked against data for conventionally manufactured steel grades. For the EMK8 material, only the endurance curve for the X-direction of the walls was seen to exhibit higher fatigue performance than the reference curves. For the 1%Ni material, the fatigue performance exceeds the references for both directions. The fracture surfaces of all failed specimens were investigated in order to characterise manufacturing imperfections and their impact on the fatigue performance.

Keywords: Wire+arc additive manufacturing, steel, fatigue, imperfections

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, wire+arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) has gained significant attention in various industries due to its ability to create large-scale, medium-complexity parts (Williams et al. [1]). Based on an arc welding process, feedstock wire is fed into an arc, thereby melting the material and depositing it onto a substrate in a layer-wise fashion (Tomar et al. [2]). Because of the historic interest of the aerospace industry in additive manufacturing (AM) techniques (NASA has been using these processes since the 2000's (Gradl et al. [3])), the majority of present day research considers titanium alloys. However, this process also has the potential to transform industries that typically use steel components. To enable the widespread adoption of WAAM in these industries, the mechanical properties (e.g. fatigue performance) of materials produced by this technology must be characterised and benchmarked against conventionally manufactured materials. In these research efforts, investigating material properties in different directions is of particular importance, as the WAAM process may result in anisotropic material behaviour ([2] and Wu et al. [4]).

Furthermore, as the adoption of WAAM continues to expand, it becomes crucial to understand the impact of manufacturing imperfections on the fatigue behaviour. Due to the arc welding nature of the process, WAAM has the inherent tendency to produce certain challenges and imperfections. These are typically the presence of residual stresses or thermal deformations, porosity, lack of fusion,

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cracks, delaminations, and spatter ([2,4], Evans et al. [5], Lin et al. [6], Chakraborty et al. [7], Jin et al. [8] and Ermakova et al. [9]). Bercelli et al. [10] found that the presence of imperfections is highly sensitive to the process parameters and Wu et al. [4] noted: “[Imperfections] in WAAM can occur for various reasons, such as poor programming strategy, unstable weld pool dynamics due to poor parameter setup, thermal deformation associated with heat accumulation (Wu et al. [11]), environmental influence (such as gas contamination) and other machine malfunctions.” They also noted that certain materials tend to be vulnerable to specific imperfections. For example, steel is prone to having a poor surface finish, residual stresses, and cracks [4].

The criticality of imperfections such as pores, cracks or lack of fusion is mostly linked to three aspects: their size, their distance from the closest free-surface and their shape (Xie et al. [12], Yadollahi and Shamsaei [13] and Romano et al. [14]). The size becomes important if it is larger than the grain size of the surrounding microstructure [13]. The location is important because imperfections close to a free surface have reduced material resistance at this side, which leads to faster crack initiation (Akgun et al. [15]). The morphology is closely related to local stress concentrations, as planar and/or irregularly shaped imperfections give rise to large stress concentrations and thus lead to accelerated crack initiation [12].

This paper presents the research activities carried out regarding the characterisation of the fatigue performance of steel components produced by WAAM. Experimentally obtained S-N curves of two different materials are benchmarked against reference curves from the “Atlas of Fatigue Curves” [16] and the standards EN 1993-1-9:2005 [17] and EN 13445-3:2009 [18]. The reference curves were determined for conventionally manufactured components of (mild) steel. Furthermore, imperfections are classified by type and their influence on the fatigue life is discussed.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Two filler materials were selected to produce specimens for fatigue testing, namely G 46 4 M21 4Si1 and T50 6 1Ni M M21 1 H5 wires (classification according to EN ISO 14341-A [19]). These materials will be referred to as EMK8 and 1%Ni, respectively. Detailed information regarding the printing parameters can be found in Nunes et al. [20].

Initially, two blocks measuring 150x150x150 mm³ were manufactured with the EMK8 wire (shown in Figure 1). 25 specimens were extracted from the first block in the X-direction (deposition direction), and 25 specimens were extracted from the second block in the Z-direction (build direction). Visual inspection of failed specimens revealed a considerable amount of weld imperfections (porosity, cracks, lack of fusion) in these blocks. It was hypothesised that lack of fusion might have been caused by deformation of the substrate plate due to the large heat input during the printing process. Such deformation, especially during the deposition of the initial layers, might have resulted in inaccurate positioning of the weld torch during deposition of the subsequent layers, leading to lack of fusion. In an effort to produce imperfection-free specimens, the same material was used to print two additional walls with a length of 300 mm, a height of 150 mm and a thickness of 25 mm (also shown in Figure 1), resulting in an additional 20 specimens in both the X-direction and Z-direction. By manufacturing thin walls rather than blocks, excessive deformation of the substrate during the deposition of the first layers was avoided. In the analysis of the S-N data in the following section, the initially printed blocks will be treated separately from the subsequently printed walls. No distinction will be made between the individual walls or blocks. As the printing parameters were not varied between individual walls or blocks, it was assumed that differences in material properties between individual walls or blocks were negligible.

For the 1%Ni material, only two walls were printed. For this material, 15 specimens were extracted for each direction. Specimens of either material with imperfections visible on the surface were not tested.

Table 1 summarises the results of tensile tests previously performed on these materials produced by WAAM. Further details have been reported in [20]. Different walls than those described above were manufactured for tensile test specimen extraction, but the same printing parameters were used.

S-N curves were determined via rotating bending fatigue tests (load ratio $R = -1$) in accordance with standard BS ISO 1143:2010 [21]. Cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 6.0 mm and reduced section length of 32.0 mm were used. After machining, the gauge section was manually polished to obtain a surface finish of $R_a < 0.2 \mu\text{m}$, which was measured (in the longitudinal direction) with a Hommel Somicronic Surfscan 3D profilometer. Figure 2 schematically shows the test setup, with the specimen loaded under four point bending in an Enduteq RR Moore rotating bending fatigue test machine. By applying a suitable combination of weights, the desired load is obtained.

TABLE 1 Tensile properties of selected materials [20]

Wire	Yield strength [MPa]	Ultimate tensile strength [MPa]	Elongation after fracture [%]	Reduction of area [%]
EMK8 (G 46 4 M21 4Si1)	483	586	32.0	74.0
1%Ni (T50 6 1Ni M M21 1 H5)	672	722	24.0	67.5

FIGURE 1 (Left) specimen extraction directions in a printed wall (specimens not to scale); (right) printed block

FIGURE 2 Schematic of the RR Moore rotating bending fatigue test setup (Hectors [22])

The statistical data analysis was guided by ISO 12107:2012 [23] and Schneider and Maddox [24]. The significance level for hypothesis testing was set at 5%. For the EMK8 material, the S-N curves were established via repeated tests at predefined loads, while the loads used to investigate the 1%Ni material were determined as a double logarithmic distribution without repeated tests as recommended by [23]. The limited number of 1%Ni specimens did not allow for repeated tests at a sufficient number of stress levels to characterise the S-N curve. Furthermore, as the S-N data typically shows more scatter for higher fatigue life, this distribution aims to address this behaviour by allocating more specimens in the higher life regimes [23]. The end criterion for the tests was set as specimen failure or applying 10 million cycles (considered as “run-out” or infinite life). Since a minimum of 30 valid observations are required to establish an S-N curve intended for design or reliability [23], the S-N curves presented in the following section should be considered only as exploratory work.

Fracture surfaces of failed specimens were investigated using a Keyence VR-5200 wide-area 3D measurement system in order to characterise any welding imperfections at which the fatigue failure had originated. As only a limited amount of specimens were available for the 1%Ni specimens and as the fracture surfaces of these specimens were free of macro-imperfections, only EMK8 specimens were considered in the analysis. The standard EN ISO 6520-1:2007 [25] was used as primary guideline to classify the observed imperfections.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

S-N curves

Figure 3 shows the linear S-N curves, in a double logarithmic diagram, obtained for the specimens extracted from the initially printed blocks with the EMK8 wire, while the S-N curves obtained from the walls printed with the same material are presented in Figure 4. The results for the 1%Ni material are shown in Figure 5. In these figures, the full line shows the best fit curve for the experimental data, as obtained by Ordinary Least Squares Linear Regression (OLSLR), which represents 50% probability of failure [23]. The dashed lines show the 97.5% confidence interval for the OLSLR S-N curve, while the dashed-dotted lines indicate the 99.7% prediction interval obtained from shifting the OLSLR curve by three standard deviations (*SD*). Some results were deemed invalid due to excessive heating of the specimen, resulting in plastic deformation.

FIGURE 3 S-N curves for specimens extracted from WAAM EMK8 blocks in X-direction (left) and Z-direction (right)

FIGURE 4 S-N curves for specimens extracted from WAAM EMK8 walls in X-direction (left) and Z-direction (right)

FIGURE 5 S-N curves for specimens extracted from WAAM 1%Ni walls in X-direction (left) and Z-direction (right)

Statistical analysis [24] of the S-N data for the EMK8 blocks does not allow rejecting the hypothesis that the datasets for the two directions follow the same linear S-N curve at a significance level of 5%. For the data obtained from the walls, this hypothesis can be rejected, indicating a significant difference between the two orientations. In other words, anisotropy is observed for the specimens extracted from the walls. A significant difference between the block and walls is present for the X-direction. However, for the Z-direction, no significant difference is found.

For the 1%Ni material, statistical testing of the datasets does not lead to the rejection of the hypothesis that the two sets follow the same S-N curve at a significance level of 5%. Therefore, no anisotropy is observed for this material.

Benchmark against standards and literature

As no S-N curve data for equivalent WAAM materials was found in literature, Figure 6 compares the experimentally obtained OLSLR S-N curves for the EMK8 and 1%Ni wires with the curve for mild steel obtained from the “Atlas of Fatigue Curves” [16]. For this comparison, it is assumed that

the curve in [16] is a best fit curve for experimental data although this is not explicitly mentioned in the reference. A rigorous statistical comparison with the experimentally determined S-N curves presented in the previous subsection is therefore not possible. In order to obtain a preliminary estimate for the fatigue limit, the experimentally obtained curves have been extrapolated to 10 million cycles (with dotted lines), although this is not strictly allowed according to [23]. It is seen that the 1%Ni material and the X-direction for the walls printed with EMK8 wire exceed the reference curve in terms of fatigue performance.

FIGURE 6 Comparison of S-N curves for WAAM EMK8 and 1%Ni wires with S-N curve for mild steel [16]

The following figures compare the experimentally established S-N data for the WAAM deposits with the design curves from EN 1993-1-9:2005 [17] and EN 13445-3:2009 [18]. For both standards, the least and most conservative curves are represented: class 160 and class 36, respectively, for EN 1993-1-9:2005 and unwelded material and class 32, respectively, in the case of EN 13445-3:2009. For unwelded regions, EN 13445-3:2009 allows both a simplified assessment (class UW) and a detailed assessment based on the ultimate tensile strength R_m , which is less conservative than the simplified approach [18]. A correction factor is provided to take the effect of surface roughness into account, which is considered if $R_z > 6 \mu\text{m}$ [18]. As the test specimens were polished (as explained in the previous section), no additional correction was required. In [24], a method is described to statistically verify if an experimentally determined S-N curve allows the use of a certain design curve. However, this method requires the standard deviation of $\log(N)$ for the design curves, which the standards do not provide. Therefore, only a qualitative visual comparison between the experimental curves and design curves is possible here.

EN 1993-1-9:2005 mentions that the design curves were determined based on the 75% confidence level of 95% probability of survival [17]. The exact procedure used to obtain these design curves from experimental data is however not explained in detail. To compare the S-N curves determined for the WAAM materials, the mean experimental curves were shifted by two standard deviations to obtain the lower 95% prediction interval (corresponding to the lower one-sided 97.5% confidence limit).

Since the fatigue assessment for welds in EN 13445-3:2009 provides design curves “approximately three standard deviations of $\log(N)$ below the mean curve” [18], the experimental

curves considered here are the lower 99.7% prediction interval obtained by shifting the OLSLR curve by three standard deviations.

As seen in Figure 7, in the high-cycle regime, the curves for the WAAM material show higher fatigue strength than the curve for class 160 from EN 1993-1-9:2005. In the low-cycle regime, the experimental curves fall below the class 160 curve, but still exceed the fatigue performance described by class 36. Compared to the curves from EN 13445:3-2009, the curve obtained for the specimens extracted in the X-direction from the walls exceeds the design curves in the high-cycle regime. While the other experimental curves show lower fatigue strength in the high-cycle region than the curve obtained from the detailed assessment, their fatigue performance exceeds the curve for class UW for the simplified assessment. Note that because of the polished surface of the specimens, the experimental curves have a flatter slope than the curves from the standards, which were determined for actual welded specimens of structural steels. For this type of specimens, the high-cycle fatigue life is dominated by fatigue crack growth, resulting in a slope of the S-N curve similar to the slope of the Paris crack growth law (Maddox [26]). However, for polished specimens, a considerable part of the fatigue life in the high-cycle regime consists of crack initiation, which results in a flatter slope of the S-N curve [26].

In Figure 8, the fatigue performance of the WAAM 1%Ni material is compared with the design curves from the standards. The fatigue performance of the WAAM material exceeds all design curves. The slopes of the experimental curves are again flatter than the slopes in the standards due to the polishing of the specimens.

FIGURE 7 Comparison of S-N curves for WAAM EMK8 wire and S-N curves from EN 1993-1-9:2005 [17] (left) and EN 13445-3:2009 [18] (right)

Fracture surfaces

Three classes of specimens were considered based on their fracture surfaces. The specimens which did not show any imperfections or where the fatigue crack did not initiate at an artifact on the fracture surface were classified as “imperfection-free”. As mentioned above, all 1%Ni specimens were classified as imperfection-free. For the (EMK8) specimens which did contain visible imperfections, the distinction between volumetric and planar imperfections was made.

The volumetric imperfections were further subdivided into micro and macro spherical pores, full and partial lack of inter-run fusion, elongated cavities, and spatter (based on EN ISO 6520-1:2007

[25]). Lack of inter-run fusion is formed when two adjacent weld beads do not fully join due to a lack of wettability, leading to a long cavity parallel to the axis of the weld beads. Figure 9 gives a schematic illustration of the formation of this type of imperfection and examples of full and partial lack of inter-run fusion. Examples of the other volumetric imperfection types are shown in Figure 10.

FIGURE 8 Comparison of S-N curves for WAAM 1%Ni wire and S-N curves from EN 1993-1-9:2005 [17] (left) and EN 13445-3:2009 [18] (right)

FIGURE 9 (Left) schematic illustration of the formation of a lack of inter-run fusion imperfection; (centre) example of full lack of inter-run fusion; (right) example of partial lack of inter-run fusion

FIGURE 10 Examples of fracture surfaces with volumetric imperfections: (left) micro pore; (centre) macro pore; (right) spatter and elongated cavity

The planar imperfections were further subdivided into in-plane and out-of-plane lack of fusion (LOF), of which examples are shown in Figure 11. Note that these two types of imperfections were found on both the specimens extracted from the X-direction and the Z-direction. This is due to the printing strategy of the WAAMED block: LOF between layers caused out-of-plane LOF for the X-direction specimens and in-plane LOF for the Z-direction specimens, while LOF between weld beads caused in-plane LOF for the X-direction specimens and out-of-plane LOF for the Z-direction specimens. This is illustrated on the right of Figure 11.

FIGURE 11 (Left) example of in-plane LOF; (centre) 3D height map of a fracture surface with an out-of-plane LOF; (right) printing strategy of a WAAMED block with examples of in-plane and out-of-plane LOF imperfections, adapted from Nunes et al. [27]

Impact of imperfections

The S-N data and types of imperfections found on the fracture surfaces of the EMK8 specimens are given in Figure 12. For the imperfections which were observed more than once, OLSLR was performed for the $(\log(N), \log(\Delta\sigma))$ data points and the resulting curve was added to the graphs. The run-out specimens were considered to be imperfection-free and were used to consider the impact of imperfections on the fatigue limit.

FIGURE 12 Impact of different imperfection types of the fatigue performance of WAAM EMK8 material in the X-direction (left) and Z-direction (right)

Note that according to the ISO 12107 standard [23] at least ten observations are needed to obtain a linear regression which is suited for “exploratory work”. As this condition is only met by the in-plane LOF imperfections, no statistical difference can be quantified between the specimens that were

imperfection-free and the ones that contained imperfections. The statements made in this section are therefore solely based on visual observations and thus should be considered with a degree of caution. Furthermore, no specimen was encountered where a single, isolated spatter imperfection was the cause of crack initiation. For this reason the impact of this type of imperfection is not included in this section.

For the X-direction specimens it appears that the in-plane LOF, out-of-plane LOF, and macro pores have a notable effect on both the slope and the intercept of the S-N curve. The effect on the fatigue limit is especially noteworthy: while several specimens reached 10 million cycles at stress levels of 450 and 548 MPa, specimens that failed at these loads all contained in-plane LOF, out-of-plane LOF, or macro pores. Note that there is no notable difference between the effect of in-plane LOF and out-of-plane LOF imperfections. This is surprising as the out-of-plane LOF imperfections are loaded in a shearing mode, which is typically considered to be less critical than an opening-type mode. Note that although the macro pores appear to have a notable impact on both the fatigue life and fatigue limit, not much more can be stated about these imperfections as only four such imperfections were observed.

For the Z-direction specimens it is observed that the lack of inter-run fusion and in-plane LOF imperfections are notably different from both the imperfection-free specimens and from each other. Note that only the intercepts of the S-N curves show pronounced differences, while their slopes remain relatively unchanged when compared to the imperfection-free specimens. Furthermore, it is remarked that the in-plane LOF appears to be more critical than the lack of inter-run fusion. This is hypothesised to be due to the planar nature of the LOF imperfections, resulting in a higher stress concentration factor at their edges compared to the volumetric lack of inter-run fusion imperfections, which accelerates the fatigue crack initiation. Note that the impact of the partial lack of inter-run fusion imperfections appears to be much less critical than the effect of the complete ones and that they seem to have no or an extremely limited effect on the fatigue limit. Again, not much more can be stated about this type of imperfection due to the limited number (four) of datapoints. The micro pores appear to result in a much steeper S-N curve. However, as only two such imperfections were observed this observation completely neglects the inherent variability which fatigue testing is known for and should thus be considered with a degree of caution. Note that as no run-out tests were obtained for the Z-direction specimens, no comments can be made on the impact of these imperfections on the fatigue limit. However, a similar effect as seen for the X-direction specimens is expected.

CONCLUSIONS

S-N curves were determined via rotating bending fatigue experiments for two directions of WAAM manufactured specimens made of EMK8 and 1%Ni wires. The procedures described in standards ISO 12107:2012 [23] and BS ISO 1143:2010 [21] were hereto adopted.

For the specimens extracted from the blocks printed with the EMK8 wire, statistical analysis did not allow concluding that there is anisotropy in fatigue properties. For the walls of the same material however, the X-direction was shown to achieve a significantly higher fatigue performance than the Z-direction. No significant anisotropy was observed for the 1%Ni material.

When comparing the experimentally obtained S-N curves of the EMK8 material with the curves from standards EN 1993-1-9:2005 [17] and EN 13445-3:2009 [18], and the S-N curve for mild steel in [16], only the curve for the X-direction of the walls was seen to exhibit higher fatigue performance than the reference curves. For the 1%Ni material, the fatigue performance exceeds the references for both X- and Z-directions. Overall, good to very good fatigue performance (comparable with design

curves for unwelded regions in the high-cycle regime) was achieved for the WAAM materials, despite the presence of imperfections. The experimental curves show a flatter slope than those in the standards due to the polished surface of the specimens.

It should be noted that the number of specimens used during these experiments is only sufficient for an exploratory investigation [23]. In order to establish curves for design or reliability purposes, additional experiments are required. Additional test data may also reduce the uncertainty of the curve fits, which may in turn influence the result of the statistical analysis when comparing the different curves.

The analysis of the impact of imperfections on the fatigue performance indicates that a general trend can be distinguished per type of imperfection. The observed macro-imperfections had a notable impact on the fatigue performance of the EMK8 material. For Z-direction specimens, planar imperfections were found to be more critical than volumetric imperfections, but did not result in an important change in slope. On the other hand, the distinction between planar and volumetric imperfections was less pronounced for the imperfections found in the X-direction specimens, but notable differences in both slope and intercept were observed due to these imperfections. However, the limited number of available specimens led to the absence of statistical significance, which meant that a comprehensive assessment of the effect of different imperfections and of the characteristic dimensions of these imperfections could not be achieved.

It is important to note that while substantial imperfections were observed, most of them originated from specimens extracted from the initially printed blocks. As welding parameters were optimised, imperfection-free fracture surfaces were consistently observed in specimens printed with these final and optimised parameters. This highlights the necessity for determining the ideal parameters for different materials and welding processes before reliable results can be obtained in WAAM. Consequently, the WAAM process cannot be considered “plug-and-play” and the establishment of appropriate parameters through iterative experimentation or previous experience is imperative.

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